

Development of novel inhibitors targeting *Mycobacterium abscessus* SAICAR synthetase (PurC) using a fragment-based approach.

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Abbreviations: SAICAR- *Phosphoribosylaminoimidazole-succinocarboxamide*; *Mab* - *Mycobacterium abscessus*; *Mtb* - *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*; *DSF* - Differential scanning fluorimetry; *ITC* – *Isothermal titration calorimetry*; *SAR* – *Structure activity relationship*; *PSA* - *Polar surface area*; *LE* – *Ligand efficiency*.

Abstract

Mycobacterium abscessus has emerged as a challenging threat to individuals with cystic fibrosis, particularly children. It is often impossible to treat the infection caused by this mycobacterium due to its intrinsic antibiotic resistance leading to lung malfunction and eventually death. Therefore, there is an urgent need to develop new drugs against novel targets in *M. abscessus* to overcome drug resistance and subsequent treatment failure. In this study, SAICAR synthase (PurC) from *Mycobacterium abscessus* (*Mab*) was identified as

a promising target for novel antibiotics. **An in-house** fragment library screen and a high-throughput X-ray crystallographic screen of diverse fragment libraries were explored to provide crucial starting points for fragment elaboration. A series of compounds developed from fragment growing and merging strategies, guided by crystallographic information and careful hit-to-lead optimisation, have achieved potent nanomolar binding affinity against the enzyme. Some compounds also show promising inhibitory effects against *Mab* and *Mtb*. This work validates PurC as a novel antimicrobial target and, utilizing a fragment-based design, demonstrates for the first time the potential to develop inhibitors against this enzyme.

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Introduction

Mycobacterium abscessus (*Mab*) is a rapidly growing species of nontuberculous mycobacteria (NTM) and is responsible for a wide range of soft tissue infections **that have** recently emerged as a major threat to individuals with cystic fibrosis, particularly children.¹⁻⁴ These infections cause accelerated inflammatory lung damage and **are often impossible to** treat due to **intrinsic antibiotic resistance, resulting in extremely high treatment failure rates** of around 55 % despite years of combination chemotherapy.^{5, 6} These infections, especially in people with cystic fibrosis, can prove fatal and are considered a **contraindication** for lung transplant to treat the lung damage caused by infections and progressive inflammatory response.^{7, 8} Therefore, there is an urgent need to develop novel drugs targeting *Mab*, as an alternative antibacterial strategy.

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Phosphoribosylaminoimidazole succinocarboxamide synthase or PurC (also known as SAICAR synthase) is an essential enzyme involved in the eighth step of *de novo* purine biosynthesis in bacteria and fungi.⁹ The enzyme catalyses the transformation of 5-aminoimidazole-4-carboxyribonucleotide (CAIR) and L-aspartate to SAICAR in the presence of adenosine triphosphate (ATP) and Mg²⁺ cofactors.^{10, 11} It is known that bacteria rely on the *de novo* pathway for **their** survival, as the pathway plays a crucial role in the synthesis of nucleic acid and nucleotide phosphate precursors for energy metabolism. Several studies in

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the past have shown that purine biosynthesis is vital for bacterial growth and persistence in the gut, blood and lungs.¹²⁻¹⁴

While most bacterial PurC enzymes exist as homo-dimers, *Mab* and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* orthologs function as monomers.¹⁵⁻¹⁸ In contrast, the human bifunctional orthologue (PAICS) is an octameric enzyme combining a central C-terminal ring of AIR carboxylase domain and an outer N-terminal SAICAR synthetase domain.¹⁹ A comparison of *Mab* PurC and the SAICAR synthetase domain of the human orthologue shows distinct structural and sequence differences, including additional insertions in the 30 amino acid longer *Mab* PurC, providing the basis for selective inhibition of this enzyme²⁰. The structural and functional differences between bacterial PurC and the human bifunctional orthologue (PAICS) makes PurC an excellent target for antimicrobial drug discovery.^{15, 19, 21, 22}

Fragment-based lead discovery has emerged as a successful approach for the identification of new drugs. Recently, the third drug derived from a fragment-based approach secured a breakthrough approval from the FDA and this methodology is seen as a reliable way forward in small-molecule drug design.²³ Fragments are low-molecular-weight small molecules with low structural complexity. The hits that come from a fragment-based screening usually exhibit lower potency than larger molecules identified from a standard high-throughput platform. However, these fragments bind by making high-quality interactions to a hotspot required for any ligand on the biomolecular target leading to highly ligand efficient (LE) molecules.^{24, 25}

In this work, the application of a fragment-based approach targeting *Mab* SAICAR synthetase (*MabPurC*) was used to discover a new class of 4-amino-6-(pyrazol-4-yl)pyrimidine based inhibitors. The fragment elaboration strategies described here utilize the hits identified from both our in-house fragment library and XChem fragment screening facilities as starting points for development²⁰. Through this study, for the first time, we were able to validate the essentiality of PurC in *Mab* and demonstrate the potential for developing inhibitors against this bacterial enzyme.

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Results and discussion

Generation of purC gene knock-out mutants

In order to assess the suitability of targeting PurC for anti-microbial drug development, essentiality studies of PurC in *M. abscessus* were performed. This approach made use of a recombineering system to generate knockout mutants in *M. abscessus subsp. massiliense*. The resulting knockouts were analysed by PCR and compared with that of the wild-type. The knockout strains did not grow in normal growth media, but colonies appeared when the media was supplemented with hypoxanthine, thus confirming the essentiality the purC gene in bacterial growth and replication (Figure S1)

Figure – Mary and Juan (include in main manuscript?)

Initial SAR Studies

Work within our group has identified several fragments that were found to bind into the adenine pocket of the ATP binding site of *M. abscessus* PurC and these were characterised using a wide range of biophysical techniques, including differential scanning fluorimetry (DSF), isothermal titration calorimetry (ITC) and X-ray crystallography²⁶. One of the hits identified from the above screening cascade was 4-amino-5-pyrimidinecarbonitrile fragment **1**. The X-ray crystal structure of *MabPurC* in complex with this fragment shows several key interactions which include i) H bonding of the amino moiety of **1** to the His69 side chain and to carbonyl of Arg91 main chain ii) H bonding of N3 of pyrimidine to the amide nitrogen of Leu93 and iii) H bonding of the nitrile nitrogen to the amide nitrogen of Asp213. These interactions are also made by the adenine ring of ATP when it binds to PurC. Along with its well-characterised interactions, this fragment has also demonstrated a ΔT_m of +3.6°C and a K_d value of 341 μ M (for ATP; K_d = 88 μ M).

A further fragment screen was also performed on *MabPurC* with a more structurally diverse compound library using the high-throughput X-ray screening approach (XChem) available at the Diamond Light Source.²⁷ With the access to the roboticised XChem facility and the use

of PanDDA data-processing software²⁸, the fragment **2** was identified and its binding interactions to *MabPurC* were characterised.²⁶ One of the distinct interactions that this fragment makes is the π -interaction between the pyridine ring of the fragment and the side chain of Arg17. The movement of the Arg side chain to accommodate the pyridine ring of fragment **2** was not previously observed from our in-house fragment screening and is not observed in the ATP bound structure (PDB Code XXXX). The flexibility of this Arg17 side chain was identified as beneficial towards further medicinal chemistry intervention to design chemical scaffolds that possess a slightly different mode of binding to that of ATP. This important aspect was therefore incorporated into a fragment-growing strategy from the ATP binding site.

Figure 1. (a and b) X-ray crystal structures of *Mab* PurC in complex with ATP (pdb code: XXXX) with the sidechain and key interactions within the active sites highlighted, (c and d) Overlay of the fragment 1 and (c) with fragment 2

Prior to hit-to-lead elaboration, further DSF was performed on a number of close analogues of fragment 1 to examine preliminary SARs around the pyrimidine pharmacophore. As shown in Table 1, a comparison of fragment 1 ($K_d = 341 \mu\text{M}$, LE 0.53) and compound 4 ($K_d = 1060 \mu\text{M}$, LE 0.45) shows that the pyrimidine analogue exhibits a higher ΔT_m and a 3-fold increase in the binding affinity compared to pyridine counterparts. The addition of a chlorine atom at 6-position of pyrimidine is tolerated as shown in compound 3 ($K_d = 159 \mu\text{M}$, LE 0.52) when compared to the original fragment 1. The replacement of a nitrile with a chlorine atom (compounds 3 vs 6) decreases ΔT_m and shows a slight decrease in binding affinity (for compound 6; $K_d = 442 \mu\text{M}$, LE 0.51). This substitution could be beneficial for fine-tuning the physicochemical properties of lead compound later in the optimisation as compounds with a

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chlorine substituent show a higher clogP and PSA compared to compounds with a nitrile functional group.²⁹ However, the removal of H-bond acceptor at this position (CN or Cl) diminishes the binding affinity completely as seen in compound **8**. This shows the significance of having H-bonding acceptor present at the 5-position of pyrimidine.

Table 1: Biophysical data for selected fragments showing the change in protein melting temperatures (ΔT_m), binding affinities (K_d) and ligand efficiencies (LE).

Compound	Chemical structure	ΔT_m ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) ^a	MabPurC K_d (μM)	LE ^c
1		+3.6	341 \pm 14	0.53
3		+4.0	159 \pm 9	0.52
4		+1.7 ^b	1060 \pm 252	0.45
5		+1.0	971 \pm 29	0.51
6		+2.5	442 \pm 22	0.51
7		+1.7	ND	-
8		+0.7	ND	-

^a 5 mM ligand and 100 μ M *MabPurC*

^b 3 mM ligand and 70 μ M *MabPurC*

^c kcal mol⁻¹ per heavy atom

ND not determined

Hit-to-Lead optimisation

Fragment **1** was thus selected for further elaboration due to its having the highest ligand efficiency (LE) in the series. A closer examination of the X-ray structure of fragment **1** with *Mab PurC* reveals a vector for elaboration in the 'ribose binding pocket', at the 6-position of pyrimidine, which could be explored as an area for fragment growth since it is tolerated as seen in compound **3**. Utilising fragment elaboration at this position would allow the possibility of adding the feature of pyridine moiety of fragment **2** into fragment **1**. The position of these two fragments are almost perpendicular to each other and therefore it is necessary that a flexible linker be identified to join the two fragments.

As shown in Table 2, the addition of a 4-pyrazolyl moiety effectively enhanced the binding affinity by an order of magnitude resulting in the identification of compound **9** ($K_d = 23 \mu$ M, LE 0.39). Even though the X-ray crystal structure of *MabPurC* in complex with compound **9** shows that the pyrazole does not make any significant polar interactions to *MabPurC* as demonstrated in Figure 2, all the original polar contacts of the pyrimidine core have been retained. It is worth noting that the attached pyrazole **9** or pyridine (compounds **10** and **11**) and the pyrimidine core align in a coplanar fashion (Figure 3).

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Table 2: Exploration of SAR on the 6-position of the pyrimidine ring against *MabPurC*

Compound	R	ΔT_m ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) ^a	<i>MabPurC</i> K_d (μM)	LE ^c
1	H	+1.1	341 \pm 14	0.53
3	Cl	+2.1	159 \pm 9	0.52
9		+4.4	23 \pm 3 ^b	0.39
10		+2.0	588 \pm 26 ^b	0.28
11		+2.6	84 \pm 10 ^b	0.33

^a 1 mM ligand and 100 μM *Mab PurC*

^b 1 mM ligand and 40 μM *Mab PurC*

^c kcal mol⁻¹ per heavy atom

Following the identification of compound **9**, guided by the structural information, various flexible groups and saturated side chains were examined in order to identify the ideal vector to incorporate without having a detrimental effect on binding affinity (Table 3). The morpholine ring was employed in a number of analogues to assist with the solubility of the compounds. The compound **14** ($K_d = 22 \mu\text{M}$, LE 0.32), which has an ethyl ester side chain, was identified and, although an increase in its binding affinity was not observed, the added hydrophobic ethyl ester was identified by X-ray crystallography close to the region where the pyridine moiety of fragment **2** is located. A similar binding mode was also observed in the X-

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ray structure of **13** ($K_d = 52 \mu\text{M}$, LE 0.26). Interestingly, the ethyl morpholine group in **13** occupies almost the same site as pyridine in fragment **2**. Even though these two compounds (**14** and **13**) did not show further improvement in binding affinity to *MabPurC*, the corresponding X-ray structures have provided the critical information necessary for further fragment optimisation.

Figure 2. (a) X-ray crystal structures of *Mab PurC* in complex with fragment **1** with the side chain and key interactions within the active sites highlighted (pdb code: XXXX), (b-d) X-ray crystal structures of *Mab PurC* in complex with compound **9**, **13** and **14** with the side chain and key interactions within the active sites highlighted (pdb codes: (**9**) XXXX, (**13**) XXXX and (**14**) XXXX).

Based on the X-ray crystal structure of *MabPurC* in complex with compound **13**, it is proposed that the incorporation of 3-pyridylmethyl moiety at the N1 of pyrazole would mimic and merge the compound characteristics that engage the π -interaction seen with the pyridine moiety of fragment **2**. The resulting compound **16** ($K_d = 3.1 \mu\text{M}$, LE 0.36) shows an order-of-magnitude increase in its binding affinity compared to compound **13**. The alignment of this pyridine ring of compound **16** in the *MabPurC* binding site by forming π -stacking interaction to Arg17 side chain is crucial for the enhanced affinity observed (Table 3).

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Table 3: Biophysical data of 4-amino-6-(pyrazol-4-yl)pyrimidine derivatives against *MabPurC*

Compound	R ¹	R ²	R ³	X	ΔT_m (°C) ^a	<i>MabPurC</i> K_d (μM)	LE ^c
9	CN	Me	H	N	+4.4	23 ± 3	0.39
12	CN		=O	N	+2.9	45 ± 5	0.27
13	CN		H	N	+3.5	52 ± 8	0.26
14	CN		H	N	+4.5	22 ± 0.8	0.32
15	CN		H	N	+2.6	47 ± 6	0.26

16	CN	3-pyridyl	H	N	+6.2	3.1 ± 0.3	0.36
17	CN	4-pyridyl	H	N	+6.0	7.5 ± 0.5	0.33
18	CN	5-methoxy-3-pyridyl	H	N	+6.5	2.1 ± 0.2	0.34
19	CN	3-fluorophenyl	H	N	+8.3	0.25 ± 0.03	0.41
20	CN	3-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl	H	N	+5.3	ND	-
21	CN	3-fluoro-5-methoxyphenyl	H	N	+8.8 ^b	ND ^d	-
22	CN	4-fluorophenyl	H	N	+9.4	0.22 ± 0.02	0.41
23	CN	Phenyl	H	N	+9.3	0.28 ± 0.03	0.43
24	CN	Phenyl	Me	N	+7.5	0.53 ± 0.03	0.38
25	CN	Benzyl	H	N	+5.3	ND	-
26	CN	3,5-difluorophenyl	H	N	+8.7 ^b	0.24 ± 0.05	0.39
27	CN	3,4-difluorophenyl	H	N	+9.0	0.15 ± 0.02	0.37
28	Cl	3-fluorophenyl	H	N	+7.1	0.35 ± 0.02	0.39
29	CN	3-fluorophenyl	H	CH	+5.1	1.4 ± 0.06	0.36

30	Cl	3-fluorophenyl	H	CH	+2.6 ^b	ND
31	H	3-fluorophenyl	H	N	+4.1	ND

^a 1 mM ligand and 100 μ M *Mab PurC*

^b 0.5 mM ligand and 100 μ M *Mab PurC*

^c kcal mol⁻¹ per heavy atom

^d due to poor solubility

ND not determined

The use of various substituted phenyl and pyridyl rings was examined to investigate further the effect of the aromatic rings in forming π interaction to Arg17. It is generally accepted that fluorobenzene is a good isostere of pyridine due to the similarity in dipole and electron density.³⁰ There are many successful examples of an aryl C-F mimicking an azine nitrogen atom in drug discovery.³⁰ This change is also deemed as a way to modulate the physicochemical properties of the compound as removing a nitrogen atom will reduce the compound's basicity and increase its clogP at the same time.³¹ A number of analogues were synthesised including pyridylmethyl and fluorobenzyl side chains. Compound **19** ($K_d = 0.25$ μ M, LE 0.41) featuring 3-fluorophenyl moiety shows another order of magnitude improvement in binding affinity while all key interactions to *MabPurC* are still observed in the corresponding X-ray crystal structure.

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Figure 3. X-ray crystal structures of Mab PurC in complex with (a) compound **16** (pdb code **XXXX**) (b) compound **19** (pdb code **XXXX**), (c) compound **24** (pdb code **XXXX**) and (d) compound **28** (pdb code **XXXX**) with the side chain and key interactions within the active sites highlighted.

The modulation of the electronic nature of this aryl ring in compound **19** is crucial to the affinity jump observed and various substituted phenyl analogues with electron-withdrawing and electron-donating groups were subsequently synthesised to test this hypothesis. The fluorine substituted compounds **22** ($K_d = 0.22 \mu\text{M}$, LE 0.41) and **27** ($K_d = 0.15 \mu\text{M}$, LE 0.37) retain a strong binding affinity as observed in compound **19**. Interestingly, compound **23** ($K_d = 0.28 \mu\text{M}$, LE 0.43), possessing an unsubstituted phenyl ring, also demonstrates good

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binding affinity. Compound **24** ($K_d = 0.53 \mu\text{M}$, LE 0.38) where a methyl group was introduced on the methylene carbon, a derivative of compound **23**, also displays a good binding affinity suggesting that this modification is tolerated this could possibly offer a further vector for elaboration.

The fragment SAR (Table 1) has shown that the interchange between the CN and Cl moieties is tolerated and the removal of N1 atom in pyrimidine has a dramatic negative effect on binding affinity. As shown in Table 3, each compound (**7**, **28**, **30**, and **31**) shares the same 3-fluorophenyl side chain as **19** but with slightly different core structure. The compound **28** ($K_d = 0.35 \mu\text{M}$, LE 0.39), possessing a chlorine atom at the 5-position of pyrimidine rather than a nitrile group, exhibits a similar binding affinity as compared to **19**, whereas compounds **29** and **30** led to a decrease in binding affinities. This observation corresponds to the results observed in early fragment SARs and could be important for further optimisation, as the derivatives containing a Cl substituent would possess a higher lipophilicity in comparison to compounds having a CN moiety and therefore could play additional roles in determining compound permeability and retention in the mycobacteria.

Phenotypic screening of compounds against *Mab* and *Mtb*

The minimal inhibitory concentrations (MIC) of the selected compounds ($K_d < 50 \mu\text{M}$) were determined for both *M. abscessus* and *M. tuberculosis in vitro* (Table 4). While most compounds elaborated from the fragments exhibited complete growth inhibition at $50 \mu\text{M}$ against both *Mab* and *Mtb*, compound **19** in the later stage of development showed more promising inhibitory activity at $25 \mu\text{M}$ against *M. abscessus* (Table 3). However, compounds **27**, **28** and **29** exhibit lower MIC against *Mtb* ($25 \mu\text{M}$) than *Mab* ($50 \mu\text{M}$) possibly due to the higher lipophilicity of these compounds, leading to a larger proportion of the compound being absorbed and retained in the *Mtb* bacterial cell. Further work is currently ongoing to optimise the compounds selectively active against *Mab*.

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Table 4: Antimycobacterial profile of 4-amino-6-(pyrazol-4-yl)pyrimidine derivatives screened against *Mab* and *Mtb*

Compound	<i>Mab</i> PurC K_d (μ M)	<i>Mab</i> MIC (μ M) ^a	<i>Mtb</i> MIC (μ M) ^b
Amikacin	NA	3.1	12.5
12	45 \pm 5	50	NA
13	52 \pm 8	50	NA
14	22 \pm 0.8	50	NA
15	47 \pm 6	200	50
16	3.1 \pm 0.3	50	50
17	7.5 \pm 0.5	50	50
18	2.1 \pm 0.2	50	50
19	0.25 \pm 0.03	25	50
22	0.22 \pm 0.02	50	50
23	0.28 \pm 0.03	50	50
24	0.53 \pm 0.03	50	50
26	0.24 \pm 0.05	50	50
27	0.15 \pm 0.02	50	25
28	0.35 \pm 0.02	50	25
29	1.4 \pm 0.06	50	25

- a) *Mycobacterium abscessus subspecies abscessus* (ATCC 19977) transformed with pmv310 plasmid expressing Lux ABDCE operon, grown in Middlebrook 7H9 broth supplemented with ADC
- b) *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* Δ leuD Δ panCD (Bleupan) transformed with pSMT1 expressing Lux AB and GFP, grown in Middlebrook 7H9 broth supplemented with 0.5% glycerol, 0.05% Tween 80 (removed for 24 h prior to experiments), 10% OADC (BD), 0.05 mg/mL L-leucine, and 0.024 mg/mL calcium pantothenate, Hygromycin and Zeocin (removed for 24 h prior to experiments).

Synthetic Chemistry

The early compounds in the series were synthesised following the routes displayed in Scheme 1. Compounds **9**, **10** and **11** were synthesised from a Suzuki coupling reaction

between pyrazole boronic acid **32** or pyridine boronic acids **33** and **34** and 4-amino-6-chloropyrimidine-5-carbonitrile **3** using Pd(*t*-Bu₃P)₂ as a catalyst in the presence of KF to afford the desired products in moderate to good yields (69 % yield for **9**, 25 % for **10** and 24 % for **11**).³² Compound **12** was synthesised from its corresponding 4-iodopyrazole **35** and 4-morpholinecarbonyl chloride to afford compound **36**. This then underwent a Miyaura borylation reaction using B₂pin₂ in the presence of Pd(dppf)Cl₂ catalyst to yield the boronate ester **37** in good yield (53 %).³³ The boronate ester **37** was then reacted with the chloropyrimidine **3** core following the Suzuki condition to obtain **12** in 37% yield. Compounds **13**, **14** and **15** were synthesised from the corresponding pyrazole boronate esters and 4-amino-6-chloropyrimidine-5-carbonitrile under the Suzuki condition to yield the products in moderate yield (32 % yield for **13**, 38 % for **14** and 19% for **15**).³²

Scheme 1. Synthesis of 4-aminopyrimidine and 2-aminopyridine derivatives

Reagents and Conditions: (a) Pd(*t*-Bu₃P)₂, KF, 1,4-dioxane, water, MW irradiation, 150 °C, 40 min; (b) 4-morpholinecarbonyl chloride, Et₃N, DCM, overnight; (c) B₂pin₂, Pd(dppf)Cl₂.DCM, KOAc, DMSO, MW irradiation, 80 °C, 3 h.

For most of the final products in the series (**16-31**), as depicted in Scheme 2, the synthesis of these compounds began with the substitution reaction between pyrazole-4-boronic acid pinacol ester and an alkyl halide of choice (**39-52**) in the presence of a carbonate base (Cs₂CO₃) to obtain the corresponding N-alkylated pyrazole boronate esters (**53-66**) in moderate to good yields (31% to quantitative yield).³⁴ The Suzuki coupling **reaction**, under the same condition using Pd(*t*-Bu₃P)₂ as a **catalyst, was** employed in the preparation of the final compounds resulting in 20-81% yield of the desired products after a flash column chromatography.³²

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Compound **7** was prepared according to the reported literature procedure starting from the bromination reaction of 4-methoxy-2-pyridone using phosphorus oxybromide (POBr₃) followed by nucleophilic amination using aqueous ammonia to replace the bromine at the 2-position of pyridine.³⁵ The compound **29** was synthesised using the same condition as that for the Suzuki coupling reaction between previously prepared compound **66** and compound **7** in 61% yield. The synthesis of **30** began with the Suzuki coupling reaction between **66** and 2,3-dichloro-4-iodopyridine **68**. The reaction proceeded well (56% yield of **69**) with 4-iodo moiety being replaced with pyrazole side chain. Compound **69** underwent a Pd-catalysed Buchwald-Hartwig reaction with benzophenone imine and the imine product obtained was then hydrolysed *in situ* under an acidic condition using 1 M HCl to afford the desired 2-aminopyridine **30** (63% yields over 2 steps).³⁶

Scheme 2. Synthesis of 4-aminopyrimidine and 2-aminopyrimidine derivatives

Reagents and Conditions: (a) Cs₂CO₃, ACN, overnight; (b) Pd(*t*-Bu₃P)₂, KF, 1,4-dioxane, water, MW irradiation, 150 °C, 40 min; (a) K₂CO₃ or Cs₂CO₃, ACN, overnight; (c) (i) Pd₂(dba)₃, BiNAP, *t*-BuONa, benzophenone imine, toluene, 80 °C, overnight (ii) 1 M HCl, THF, 5 h.

Conclusion

The application of fragment-based approach towards the discovery of novel inhibitors of *M. abscessus* PurC are described. A combination of in-house fragment screening and high-throughput X-ray crystallographic screen provided crucial starting points for the fragment elaboration process. The fragment growing and merging strategies combined the structural characteristics of the two parent fragments, fragment 1 and fragment 2. The hit-to-lead elaboration, guided by X-ray crystallographic information and binding affinity data, resulted in the identification of compound 19 (K_d 250 nM, LE 0.41) and compound 27 (K_d 150 nM, LE 0.37), both possessing promising *in vitro* binding affinities and MIC against *M. abscessus* and *M. tuberculosis*. The fragment growing and merging approaches described here, further demonstrates the strength of fragment-based design in accelerating the overall hit-to-lead

progression. These results are encouraging and this study, as a first example of designing inhibitors against bacterial PurC, shows the potential for developing novel anti-microbials targeting this enzyme. Work is currently underway to improve the overall physico-chemical profiles of the lead compounds in order to improve their affinity against *M. abscessus*.

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Author Contributions

CA, AGC, TLB, RAF and MJ designed and supervised the project. SC, AC, AJW synthesised the compounds used in this study. SET, MAGE and VM carried out the structural biology and biochemical studies. KB devised and carried out the screening of the compounds against *Mab* and *Mtb*. JMB and MJ generated the knockout mutants. SC, SET and AGC wrote the manuscript and all authors commented on the final version of the manuscript.

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Graphical Abstract

